

Effect of Self Efficacy and Motivation on Performance

Sadhika Katiyar (Research Scholar, Bundelkhand University)

Dr. Aparna Raj (Professor, Institute of Tourism and Hotel Management, Bundelkhand University)

ABSTRACT:

Self-efficacy is the confidence of individual on his competencies and abilities. Level of self-efficacy impacts motivation, emotion and thoughts. Motivation acts as driving force for employees to attain specific goals and objectives. Motivation is indispensable factor to achieve the organizational goals. Main aim of the study was to analyse the individual research findings pertaining to the relationship between self-efficacy, motivation and employee performance. During study it was observed that both self-efficacy and motivation theories can be practically applied in the organizations to improve work performance of employees.

Keywords: Self-efficacy, Employees performance, Motivation

INTRODUCTION:

Employees performance is the key to success of any organization. The daily performance of employees may lead to success or failure of any business. To stay competitive and successful in today's world, companies should constantly try to bring out best performance from their employees. Motivation is a force that inspires employees to give their best efforts and performance for the benefit of the organization. Motivation improves the performance of individual which in turn enhances the efficiency of organization. Performance of employee depends on many factors, motivation and self-efficacy were taken in this study. Self-efficacy is person's belief in his/her capabilities. Self-efficacy can be acquired through self-learning and experience. Without well-developed self-efficacy, individual may be lacking in self-confidence and leadership. The employee performance is strongly influenced by their motivation and self-efficacy.

When a person tries hard to attain a certain goal, he is said to be motivated. Motivation is necessary for good performance but not sufficient. Ability and environmental factors also play an important role in performance. Ability is to have required skills and knowledge to perform the job. Environmental factors like information, resources and necessary support to perform, play crucial role in employee productivity.

Definition of Variables:

Motivation:

Term 'motivation' is derived from motive, which facilitates good performance from the employees. Motivation of employee works as a force which acts as a catalyst to achieve desired result from employees. Need, drives and incentives are three interdependent elements necessary for motivation (Miner, J.B., Ebrahimi, B., & Wachtel, J.M.1995).

According to Luthan (1998) motivation is “a process that starts with a physiological deficiency or need that activates a behaviour or a drive that is aimed at a goal incentive.” Motivation is the extent to which individual tries hard to achieve a set goal (Mitchell, 1982) said.

Thus, motivation can be explained as the extent to which an individual wants and tries to engage himself in certain specified behaviours.

Self-Efficacy:

Bandura (1997) defined self-efficacy as a person’s belief in his own capacity to make an effort required for goal attainment. There are three dimensions of self-efficacy: *magnitude*, the extent of difficult task an employee believe he can attain; *strength*, the assurance about magnitude as strong or weak; *generality*, the limit to which the expectation is generalized across situations.

Employee Performance:

Performance comprises of outcome of performed tasks based on their knowledge, skills and expertise. In organizational setting performance is accumulated result of effort, skill and abilities contributed in improved productivity to achieve organizational goal. Better employee performance means efforts towards organizational goal achievement also requiring more efforts to improve performance (Ellinger et al, 2003). Management practices also play important role in improving employee performance. Internal satisfaction of employee also plays an important role in improving employee performance. (Harter et al, 2002).

Research Methodology:

Type of Study: Exploratory

Data collection: Secondary data

Limitations:

Research was limited to management journals, organizational psychology journals and online journals to understand the employee engagement and job satisfaction variables and to explore the relationship between them.

Motivation and Employee Performance:

Reference	Area of Study	Research Method	Study Sector	Dependent(D)/Independent (ID)
(Kuswati, 2020)	Motivation	Quantitative	Central Govt./Indonesia	ID: Motivation D: Employee Performance
(Alase & Akinbo, 2021)	Motivation	Quantitative	Bank/Nigeria	ID: Motivation D: Performance
(Ibrahim &	Motivation	Quantitative	Micro Finance	ID: Motivation

Brobbeey, 2015)			Company/Ghana	D: Performance
(Ekundayo, 2018)	Motivation	Quantitative	Insurance Companies	ID: Motivation D: Employee Performance
(Nabi, Islam, Dip, & Hossain, 2017)	Motivation	Quantitative	Bank/Bangladesh	ID: Motivation D: Employee Performance
(Siddiqui & Rida, 2019)	Motivation	Quantitative	Bank/Pakistan	ID: Motivation D: Employee Performance

Kuswatim, (2020) investigated on government employees of Indonesia. Population in this study was 103 government officials with 82 sample size. Questionnaire was main tool to collect data relevant for the research. Research findings says that motivation have a strong, positive impact on employee performance.

(Alase & Akinbo, 2021) conducted a research survey using five-point Likert scale questionnaire on 206 bank employees and stated that higher performance from employee can be exerted through motivation. They further revealed that monetary and non-monetary incentives have high correlation with employee performance.

(Ibrahim & Brobbee, 2015) tried to examine the effect of motivation on employee performance on 80 selected respondents and result showed that organizational performance of motivated employees could be seen in the form of increased efficiency, employee satisfaction, helping employees to meet their personal goals and good bond of employees with organization.

The study conducted by (Ekundayo, 2018) on 100 respondents and stated that motivation strongly affects performance which means there is a positive relationship that exists between motivation and their performance. The study hence suggested that motivational tools should be studied thoroughly to select most effective tool. Fringe benefits, Bonus, Promotion policy, involvement in decision making and rotation of employees are some motivational tools.

According to (Nabi, Islam, Dip, & Hossain, 2017) effectiveness and efficiency of employees highly increase if they are motivated. In this study de-motivation factors which negatively affects employee performance were also focused.

(Okine, Addeh, Olusola, & Asare, 2021) identified motivation as strong determinant of employee satisfaction and performance. Motivational strategies should be selected carefully because each strategy has its consequences. Hence need of employees should be examined before choosing any practice.

Self-Efficacy and Employee Performance:

Reference	Area of Study	Research Method	Study Sector	Dependent(D)/Independent (ID)
(Machmud, 2018)	Self-Efficacy	Quantitative	Govt. institutions	ID: Self-efficacy D: Satisfaction, Work-related performance
(Yulanie & Irawanto, 2021)	Self-Efficacy	Quantitative	Education (R&D)	ID: Self-efficacy D: Job Performance
(Srivastava & Pathak, 2019)	Self-Efficacy	Quantitative	Bank	ID: Self-efficacy, Organizational Commitment, Job Involvement D: Job Performance
(Abun, Nicolas, Apollo, Magallanes, & Encarnacion, 2021)	Self-Efficacy	Quantitative	College	ID: Self-Efficacy D: Work Performance Mediator: Work Environment
(Hidayat & Panjaitan, 2022)	Self-Efficacy	Quantitative	Dealim Indonesia Pt.	ID: Self-Efficacy, Talent Management, continuous Improvement D: Employee Performance
(Ghafoor, Qureshi, Azeemi, & Hijazi, 2011)	Self-Efficacy	Quantitative	Bank	ID: Transformational leadership style, Performance orientation Mediator: Creative self-efficacy D: Employee creativity
(Liu, Siu, & Shi, 2009)	Transformational leadership	Quantitative	Various Industries	ID: Transformational leadership, well-being Mediator: Trust D: Self-efficacy

(Machmud, 2018) tries to find out the impact of self-efficacy on satisfaction, work perception, and task performance. The sample size of the study was 69. Partial least squares approach (PLS) was used to analyse

data and concluded result as self-efficacy positively effects satisfaction and work-related performance. The study also stated that self-efficacy improves satisfaction and work perception.

(Yulanie & Irawanto, 2021) during a study within generation X and generation Y to identify the self-efficacy differences and also analysed impact on job performance of private company employee. Total 80 questionnaires were distributed out of which 62 questionnaires were filled properly. Result showed is no significant difference between self-efficacy between generations X and Y on their performance.

(Abun, Nicolas, Apollo, Magallanes, & Encarnacion, 2021) conducted a study on self-efficacy and work performance as mediated by the work environment. The study suggested that self-efficacy and work performance both are affected by work environment along with three dimensions of work performance i.e., counterproductive work behaviour, task performance and contextual performance.

A survey done by (Srivastava & Pathak, 2019) on 150 private bank employees of Uttar Pradesh and Uttarakhand, to identify the impact of self-efficacy, organizational commitment and job involvement on job performance. Result showed significant relationship between self-efficacy and job performance while insignificant impact of organizational commitment and job involvement on employee's job performance.

(Hidayat & Panjaitan, 2022) tried to find out the impact of self-efficacy, talent management, and continuous improvement on employee performance. Data was collected from 110 respondents. The study revealed that self-efficacy has partially positive and significant effect on employee performance.

(Ghafoor, Qureshi, Azeemi, & Hijazi, 2011) during a study of banking industry collected data from 176 employees predicted that self-efficacy acts as mediator between performance and creativity of the employees. Study also concluded that there is not any mediator between transformational leadership and creativity of employees.

The relationship between leadership, self-efficacy and employee satisfaction was tested by (Liu, Siu, & Shi, 2009). The results showed the mediating role of self-efficacy in the association between leadership and employee satisfaction and performance.

Conclusion:

It can be concluded from above studies that self-efficacy can motivate employees and improve their performance. Many research scholars and experts are interested in self-efficacy. Most of the studies have focused on the student's learning efficacy while minimum attention has been given on employees' self-efficacy (Gist & Mitchell, 1992;). More studies are required in this field to identify the results of improved self-efficacy. It will help to motivate them and also to improve their performance. Few implications drawn from the study are: Firstly, Overall self-efficacy of employees positively impacts their performance at workplace. Secondly, task complexity tends to moderate the relationship between self-efficacy and performance.

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